

A TALE OF RESILIENCE: AN ANALYSIS OF DISSOLVED AND NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN SECTOR SURVIVING UNTIL 2018

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Abstract:

This article delves into the dynamic interplay of entrepreneurship within the Romanian Mountain Sector by examining the landscape of dissolved and newly established enterprises that not only weathered the challenges of their initial years but thrived to survive until 2018. Through a comprehensive analysis, this study aims to shed light on the factors influencing the resilience and sustainability of businesses within the picturesque Romanian mountainous terrain.

1. Introduction:

The Romanian Mountain Sector provides a unique backdrop for entrepreneurial endeavors, where businesses face distinctive challenges and opportunities. This article explores the intricate journey of enterprises that

navigated the complexities of their early years, enduring to contribute to the region's economic landscape until 2018.

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2. Methodology:

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Utilizing a thorough quantitative approach, this research synthesizes data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators, including survival rates, reasons for dissolution, and characteristics of newly established enterprises that thrived, are examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Sector.

3. Survival and Dissolution Patterns:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the survival and dissolution patterns of enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Sector. Metrics such as the survival rate, reasons for business closures, and industry-specific challenges are scrutinized to assess the resilience and vulnerability of businesses in this unique geographic area.

4. Characteristics of Surviving Enterprises:

The paper delves into the characteristics of enterprises that not only survived but thrived until 2018 in the Romanian Mountain Sector. Insights into industry sectors, growth strategies, and adaptation to changing market conditions provide a nuanced perspective on the qualities that contribute to long-term success.

5. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic contributions of surviving enterprises, the article investigates their impact on the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. Understanding the role of these businesses in shaping the economic landscape of the Romanian Mountain Sector is essential.

6. Lessons Learned and Opportunities:

Drawing lessons from the experiences of both dissolved and surviving enterprises, this section provides insights into opportunities for improvement and growth. Understanding the challenges faced by businesses

in the mountainous terrain offers valuable information for policymakers, stakeholders, and aspiring entrepreneurs.

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7. Future Perspectives:

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Identifying trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on the Romanian Mountain Sector's entrepreneurial landscape. Considerations such as technological advancements, changing consumer behaviors, and emerging market trends are explored.

8. Results:

The paper realized statistics for the dissolved enterprises and newly established enterprises, the degree of entropy being considerable in the Romanian mountain area. Entropy opposed negentropy and it is a better modality of activities development. This type of entropy could be resolved through negentropy, as explained in "Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis": "when we tend to organize a system which, in this case is an overlap with negentropy through various activities" (Covaci Mihai & Covaci Brîndușa, 2023).

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, so 24347.56, 2998.399, 21223.00, 8995.196, 80913544.278, .912, .717, -.544, 1.400, 25258, 14128, 39386, 17925.00, 21223.00, 33323.00 .

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -5.046E-17, 4.506E-16, -1.110 E-15, 7,772E-16, -1,110E-15, -9,326E-16; R-square -5.046E-17, 4.506E-16, -1.110E-15, 7.772E-16, -1.110E-15, -9.326E-16; RMSE 2074,103, 2644,193, 132,879, 8995,196, 132,879, 167,591; MAPS 62,206, 90,648, 18,470, 330,454, 18,470, 18,701; MaxAPE 162,131, 229,226, 40,617, 833,682, 40,617, 41,104; MAE 1515.042, 2102.601, 103.185, 7331.185, 103.185, 129.244;

MaxAE 4319,677, 4919,051, 218,889, 15038,444, 218,889, 296,289;

Normalized BIC 14.199, 2.460, 10.023, 18.453, 10.023, 10.357.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I3 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 8995.196, 31.278, 7331.185; S2-Model_2: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 592.426, 18.470, 439.852; S3-Model_3: -2,220E-16, -2,220E-16, 1191,489, 29,359, 868,815; S4-Model_4: .000, .000, 2037,186, 19,625, 1444,148; S5-Model_5: .000, .000, 611,761, 26,798, 418,667; S6-Model_6: -1,110E-15, -1,110E-15, 306,437, 25,154, 233,481; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 741,010, 56,537, 512,296; S8-Model_8: 7.772E-16, 7.772E-16, 132.879, 21.432, 103.185; S9-Model_9: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 4170.083, 70.677, 2759.679; S10-Model_10: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 3402.596, 330.454, 2082.519; S11-Model_11: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 634.075, 54.486, 471.630.

Table 20. Prediction analysis for I3

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348	24348
	UCL	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091	45091
	LCL	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605	3605
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310	2310
	UCL	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676	3676

	LCL	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799	2799
	UCL	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546	5546
	LCL	51	51	51	51	51	51	51	51
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326	7326
	UCL	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023	12023
	LCL	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628	2628
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484	1484
	UCL	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894	2894
	LCL	73	73	73	73	73	73	73	73
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	1180
	UCL	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887	1887
	LCL	473	473	473	473	473	473	473	473
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140	1140
	UCL	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848	2848
	LCL	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569	-569
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	528	528	528	528	528	528	528	528
	UCL	834	834	834	834	834	834	834	834
	LCL	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577	4577
	UCL	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193	14193
	LCL	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039	-5039
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783	1783
	UCL	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630	9630
	LCL	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063	-6063
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221	1221
	UCL	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684

	LCL	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241	-241
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Figure 3.11. Graphical forecasting analysis for I3

Regarding newly established enterprises in the last three years that survived, the related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 16094.36, 1111.198, 15179.00, 3685.428, 13582380.655, 2.149, .661, 5,384, 1,279, 12744, 13181, 25925, 13256.00, 15179.00, 16757.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,1,0); S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(1,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .112, .267, -6.661E-16, .832, -6.661E-16, -6.217E-16; R-squared -.080, .877, -2.695, 1.000, -2.695, -1.887; RMSE 45,886, 78,491, .000, 277,870, .000, 1,085; MAPS 51,131, 35,053, .000, 125,989, .000, 5,353; MaxAPE 229,221, 212,031, .000, 745,455, .000, 17,476; MAE 31,479, 52,681, .000, 185,488, .000, .853; MaxAE 109,458,

202,905, .000, 721,727, .000, 1,773; Normalized BIC 6.218, 2.838, 2.790, 11.472, 2.790, 2.856.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I4 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 277.870, 34.516 ; S2-Model_2: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 65.431, 21.625; S3-Model_3: .000, -2,695, 43,090, 60,967; S4-Model_4: .832, .334, 92.930, 66.903; S5-Model_5: -6.661E-16, -6.661E-16, 22.225, 33.599; S6-Model_6: .000, .000, 11,912, 78,902; S7-Model_7: .397, .397, 4.941, 17.844; S8-Model_8: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 3.618, 88.786; S9-Model_9: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 17.767, 37.612; S10-Model_10: .000, .000, 6,578, 125,989; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 4.268, 46.835.

Table 21. Prediction analysis for I4

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	543	543	543	543	543	543	543
	UCL	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162	1162
	LCL	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	162	162	162	162	162	162	162
	UCL	308	308	308	308	308	308	308
	LCL	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	21	3	-14	-32	-49	-67	-84
	UCL	118	141	154	163	168	172	173

	LCL	-77	-135	-183	-227	-267	-306	-342
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	33	12	-9	-30	-50	-71	-92
	UCL	243	223	203	184	164	144	125
	LCL	-178	-199	-221	-243	-265	-287	-308
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
	UCL	114	114	114	114	114	114	114
	LCL	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	22	22	22	22	22	22	22
	UCL	49	49	49	49	49	49	49
	LCL	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	22	26	23	25	24	24	24
	UCL	33	39	37	38	38	38	38
	LCL	11	13	10	11	10	10	10
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	UCL	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
	LCL	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
	UCL	74	74	74	74	74	74	74
	LCL	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5
S10-Model_10:	Forecast	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
	UCL	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	LCL	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6	-6
S11-Model_11:	Forecast	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
	UCL	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
	LCL	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2

Figure 3.12. Graphical forecasting analysis for I4

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article offers a comprehensive analysis of dissolved and newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Sector that survived until 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial dynamics in this unique geographic area, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

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